

Research Tools and Services by Health Science Libraries to Support Researchers

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ABSTRACT

Health sciences libraries that engage in research gather knowledge for effective practice and develop research collaborations with people both inside and outside the profession. These guides' research resources and tools will assist the researcher in using, creating, and using evidence in daily practice and in promoting high-quality health care. The main aim of this paper we know modern research tools, and services. The services of health science libraries for the researchers Ask Librarian, citation management tools, copyright guidance, measures and increase the research impact tools and strategies including ORCID (open research contributor identifier), research data service, can assist both aspiring and experienced health information workers to learn more about the research process, typical research methods, successful design and assessment procedures and networking opportunities, and much more. Health sciences professionals who conduct research obtain knowledge effectively.

KEYWORDS: Ask librarian, Zotero, ORCID, Copyright Guide, web of science, copyright.

INTRODUCTION

University libraries play a significant role in supporting research and academic activities. Libraries have traditionally provided services related to information availability to students, employees, and other researchers. However, the nature of library contents and services is constantly evolving in today's digital world. In the twenty-first century, university libraries not only support students' regular studies, but they also serve as a significant resource for researchers. University libraries help their parent institutions' research output by boosting the efficiency and efficacy of research innovation. As a result of rapid technology breakthroughs, libraries' instructional role has emerged, and their job has grown more complicated, broad, and demanding.

OBJECTIVES

- As a library service, to be aware of the various citation management tools
- To be aware of the librarian's copyright advice for students and teachers
- To be aware of the most important source of citation analysis
- To learn more about the research data service
- By library, two people are aware of the ORCID service.

1.0 What is a research tool?

Research tools are vehicles that help in research and associated activities in general. Researchers can use "Research Tools" to collect, organize, analyze, visualize, and disseminate research findings. Dr. Nader has gathered over 800 resources to help students navigate the research process and create high-quality research outputs with greater precision and efficiency.

Ask a librarian

Students, educators, and other staff members can use Ask Librarian to ask questions about libraries and research. At any point throughout your research or project, a Librarian can assist you in locating Library resources, connecting with a Specialist, or seeking support. Ask a Librarian is a virtual service provided by libraries.

2.0. Citation Management Tools

Citation management (sometimes referred to as bibliographic or reference management) is an essential part of the research process. You must maintain track of your sources in order to correctly cite them. The Libraries offer a variety of citation management tools that make it easier to organize, retrieve, save, cite, and exchange references. EndNote, RefWorks, and Zotero are citation management programs.

2.1 EndNote

EndNote simple is a cloud-based version of EndNote that is particularly beneficial for researchers who need to collaborate or study from many computers. Although EndNote desktop and EndNote basic are designed to work together, they can also be used separately. From within EndNote or Web of Science, you can create a free EndNote basic account.

2.2 RefWorks

ProQuest's research solutions team created RefWorks. RefWorks' objective is to enable researchers to uncover new information and to provide research and librarians with tools to make their job and study more efficient.

- Save full-text documents and references from key online resources and websites to access your papers and references from any computer with RefWorks.
- Organize, highlight, and annotate your materials to cite and footnote references from your RefWorks library in your study paper.
- Create a bibliography or a list of books cited in any citation format automatically.

2.3 Zotero

Zotero is a free citation management program that allows you to collect, organize, and format citations and bibliographies. It detects content on any internet page and adds citations and, in many cases, full-text publications to your library with a single click. You may create a bibliography (reference page) or add footnotes in a variety of citation styles using Zotero. You can also share libraries with others, which is useful if you're dealing with colleagues outside of Rutgers who don't have subscription software like EndNote or RefWorks.

3.0 Copyright guide as library service

Universities contribute to the creation, protection, and transmission of ideas and insights through research, teaching, and service, and libraries must give copyright assistance to students, professors, and other workers involved in academic research and publication. The government's copyright policy aims to establish an environment in which students can achieve this admirable goal. Understanding how to use copyrighted works in research, scholarship, and teaching, as well as how to manage one's copyrighted works, is a crucial part of academic life.

Understanding copyright and other intellectual property issues is essential for promoting worldwide digital research, online education, and information sharing, as well as for developing socially useful and innovative digital technology applications. The University Libraries can assist the university's faculty, students, and staff in achieving their goals..

3.1 Copyright guide to students and Staff

Whether we realize it or not, copyright supports our daily activity at the institution. Copyright law applies to students and teachers who generate assignments, projects, papers, and theses, as well as when they use other people's works to support their scientific and educational work and replicate resources in any format and on any platform. There are two sides to copyright

- Your rights in the copyrighted works you're creating: Assignments, Projects, papers, and thesis, etc.
- The rights of other authors or creators in the copyrighted you are using
- Students must ensure that their usage of copyrighted content does not infringe on the rights of others.

3.2 General rules for using other authors work

Students and faculty members are required to produce work that is unique and creative. At the same time, the scholarly method necessitates integrating and expanding on previous research. This usually means citing other authors, using visuals (photographs, charts, infographics, graphs, and maps) to visualize concepts, repurposing data, and incorporating musical pieces, sound recordings, and visual effects into your writing.

Objectives

- Fair use encourages you to utilize an amount that is reasonable for your research goals and is tightly linked to critical examination.
- Provide attribution in the form of a citation at all times.
- A credit line to the archive is usually included when using archival material.

- Ascertain that there are no problems about privacy and publicity rights, confidentiality, patents, trademarks, contracts, licenses, or other rules or regulations that would infringe on others' rights.
- The market for the original work should not be harmed by the uses.
- If the works you want to utilize are covered by a license agreement, you should read the terms. Many internet licenses allow for nonprofit scholarly applications or allow for the fair use of content.
- In general, without the consent of the copyright holder, you should not edit or modify any third-party work that is being used.

For uses that go beyond fair use or for which fair use does not apply, it is the student's responsibility to seek licenses. Your instructor may be able to assist you in determining whether or not third-party works are being used fairly.

4 Research Data Service

Research data management is the process of planning, organizing, disseminating, and keeping the data and documentation needed to produce published research output. Government agencies and other granting organizations are increasingly mandating data management solutions that address these concerns in order for the results of funded research to be utilized by the general public.

At the Health Sciences libraries

- Consult on compliance with National Institute of Health Data Management and Sharing Policy
- Offer training workshops on using Data Management Plan Tool to develop data management plans for NIH grant proposals.
- Locate suitable data repositories.
- Provide data visualization advice and training.

5.1 Research Impact

Scholarly influence has traditionally been measured using scholarly metrics such as citation analysis, which counts the number of times an author's work has been cited by other academics. The journal impact factor is used as a proxy for journal quality in a range of fields. As new avenues for sharing scholarly knowledge are formed, traditional criteria are no longer sufficient to offer a comprehensive picture of an article's or author's scholarly effect. Alternative or supplementary measurements, coined altmetrics, have evolved in this ever-changing research context. These new criteria are combined with others to provide a more complete picture of scholarly impact. Web of Science, Scopus, and Google are just a few of the resources available.

5.1 Web of Science

The database Web of Science indexes scientific journals, books, conferences, reports, and other sorts of publications. The core topic areas include sciences, social sciences, and arts and humanities. The platform's base is the Web of Science Core Collection, which indexes over 20,000 scholarly papers and includes over 1 billion referred references. Every item in the Core Collection has an index that includes authors, affiliations, and referred references.

In addition to the Core Collection, Web of Science provides access to a variety of regional, subject, and format-specific databases. On the Web of Science platform, databases can be searched together or separately.

5.2 Scopus

Scopus is an Abstracting and indexing leading scholarly database of scholarly journals, books series, conference proceedings, trade publications, and patents. It covers the life sciences, physical sciences, health sciences, social sciences, arts, and humanities. In total, it indexes over 75 million items, including articles from over 24,000 journals by over 5,000 international publishers. Journals indexed in Scopus are selected by committees of subject matter experts, who evaluate each journal's policies, content, standing, regularity of publication, and online availability.

Scopus has a lot of different search possibilities. Authors, affiliations, abstracts, and cited references are all included in the indexing for each publication. Scopus can be used to locate related publications based on shared references, authors, themes, or keywords once you've found a document of interest.

Scopus also includes various tools for analyzing journals, authors, and institutions. The Journal Analyzer allows you to compare journals using multiple metrics, including CiteScore, SNIP, and SJR. You can use this tool to help find the best journal in which to publish your research.

5.3 Google Scholar

Anyone can use Google to search a wide range of scholarly literature from across the world, including journals, books, theses, dissertations, conference papers, preprints, and scientific documents. Among the sources are academic publishers, professional organizations, university repositories, and other scholarly websites. New publications are added to Google Scholar on a regular basis.

6.0 ORCID as Library Service

The ORCID Open Research Contributor Identifier (ORCID) is a free and permanent digital identity that allows you to easily interact with funding agencies, publishers, and colleagues. ORCID id helps researchers construct a more integrated research environment by increasing the visibility of their researcher profiles. Librarians must assist in the creation of ORCID and raise knowledge of the tool's benefits.

6.1 Benefits of using ORCID

- You will be recognized by every other researcher, including those with the same name as you.
- Your research results and efforts will be credited to you accurately.
- Your contributions and associations will be traced back to you reliably and simply.
- Filling out paperwork will take less time (giving more time for research!).
- You'll benefit from more visibility and recognition.
- You'll be able to link your record to an increasing number of organizations, funders, and publishers.
- Your ORCID record is yours to keep for the rest of your life, for free.

CONCLUSION

In the twenty-first century, the importance of librarians in research supported by Clinical Scientific and Science Awards awarded to colleges and universities, as well as the impact such awards have on expanding library services to meet the needs of researchers, cannot be overstated. In a number of situations, medical librarians are increasingly being called for assistance in assessing the validity and impact of academic research. To assist their scholars with their research, health science librarians are kept up to date with new research tools and services.

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